

STUDIES ON THE FRIES REARRANGEMENT. PART IV

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Fries rearrangement with esters of crotonic acid has been studied.

In a number of papers of this series (Sen and Misra, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 393, 1949, 26, 149, 337) Fries rearrangement has been studied with esters of unsaturated aliphatic acids. In the present paper this reaction has been extended to esters of crotonic acid, which has a smaller number of carbon atoms than those already described. As in the previous cases, esters of phenol, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresols have been prepared. These esters on treatment with anhydrous aluminium chloride rearranged mainly into *ortho*-hydroxyketones (about 60-68%) which were characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

It may be pointed out that acrylyl chloride on treatment with aluminium chloride in the presence of benzene is known to give 1-hydrindone (Kohler, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1909, 42, 375). In this case this possibility is ruled out as the product obtained gave the Baeyer's permanganate test and decolorised bromine in carbon tetrachloride, thus proving the presence of double bond in the molecule. Perhaps the presence of a methyl group in the α -position inhibits the cyclisation to hydrindone.

The effect of temperature and solvent has also been studied with the *p*-cresyl ester of crotonic acid. The solvents used were chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene, tetrachloroethane and toluene and the temperature maintained at 100° except in the case of nitrobenzene (80°). The addition of solvent instead of improving the yields resulted in considerable lowering of yields and involved considerable experimental difficulty. From this study of effect of temperature the optimum condition arrived at for the rearrangement was found to be 140°, with 1.5 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride and a reaction time of two hours.

EXPERIMENTAL

Crotonyl Chloride.—From crotonic acid (20 g.), suspended in 200 c.c. of petrol-ether, and 55 g. of thionyl chloride, 22 g. of crotonyl chloride were obtained by following the method of Staudinger *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1916, 49, 1991), b.p. 123°-124° (Staudinger *et al.* report b.p. 124°-126°).

Phenyl Ester of Crotonic Acid.—To phenol (9.4 g.), taken in a 100 c.c. flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a dropping funnel, was gradually added crotonyl chloride (10.4 g.) and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours. After cooling and addition of water the ester separated out as an oil which was taken up in ether, washed with 1% caustic soda and finally with water. The ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed by distillation. The residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 161°/11mm., yield 11.5 g. (Found: C, 73.99; H, 6.21. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 74.07; H, 6.17 per cent).

o-Cresyl ester of crotonic acid was prepared as above from *o*-cresol (10.8 g.) and the acid chloride (10.4 g.), yield 10 g., b.p. 177°/11 mm. (Found : C, 75.12 ; H, 6.88. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.81 per cent).

m-Cresyl ester of crotonic acid was prepared as above from 10.8 g. of *m*-cresol as light green oil, yield 10 g., b.p. 189°/10mm. (Found : C, 75.09 ; H, 6.87. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 75.0 ; H, 6.81 per cent).

p-Cresyl ester of crotonic acid was obtained as above from 10.8 g. of *p*-cresol, yield 11g., b.p. 181°/10mm. (Found : C 75.19 ; H, 6.92. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 75.0 ; H, 6.81 per cent).

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters

To finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.48 *M*), taken in a 200 c.c. round bottom flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a dropping funnel, was gradually added 0.035*M* of the appropriate ester. The temperature of the external bath was raised to 140° and the mixture heated at this temperature for 2 hours. On cooling and addition of ice and dilute hydrochloric acid to the puffy mass, an oil separated out. It was taken up in ether, washed successively with water, 1% sodium carbonate solution and finally with water. After dehydration, the ether was removed and the residual oil distilled in vacuum. The distillate conformed to Pyman's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280) for *o*-hydroxy-ketones.

These ketones thus obtained were all converted into the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones which were recrystallised from hot toluene.

TABLE I

Products of the Fries rearrangement of the above esters.

<i>o</i> -Hydroxy-ketones.	B.p.	Dinitrophenylhydrazone		Nitrogen	
		M.p.	Mol. formula.	Found.	Calc.
(a)	140°/10 mm.	169°	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2$	16.58%	16.37%
(b)	156°/11	174°	$C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2$	16.66	15.73
(c)	155°/10	167°	$C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2$	15.89	..
(d)	166°/10	178°	$C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2$	15.45	..

(a) = 1-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-but-2-en-1-one
(Found: C, 73.62; H, 6.56. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 74.07; H, 6.17%).

(b) = 1-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methylphenyl)-but-2-en-1-one
(Found: C, 74.58; H, 7.08. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.81%).

(c) = 1-(2'-hydroxy-4'-methylphenyl)-but-2-en-1-one
(Found: C, 74.68; H, 6.98. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.81%).

(d) = 1-(2'-hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl)-but-2-en-1-one
(Found: C, 74.86; H, 7.12. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.81%).

Temperature Effect.—In all the following five experiments *para*-cresyl ester of crotonic acid (2g.) was added to finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.4 g) and the reactions carried out at five different temperatures. Except in the case where the reaction tem-

perature was 10°, which was left for a week, the time employed was two hours. After the completion of the reaction the usual procedure, as described in the preceding page, was adopted, but the *o*-hydroxy-ketone instead of being distilled was isolated as a yellow crystalline sodium salt by the addition of dilute caustic soda to the ethereal solution. The crystalline derivative was filtered at the pump, washed with ether, and decomposed by dilute HCl when the *o*-hydroxy-ketone separated out as an oil. It was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed by evaporation. The residual oil was dried at 100° and subsequently weighed. The results are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Temperature.	Time.	Yield of the <i>o</i> -hydroxy-ketone.
10°	7 days	No effect—only in traces
100°	2 hours	0.3 g.
120°	"	1.0 g.
140°	"	1.3 g.
165°	"	1.8 g. but accompanied with charring.

Solvent Effect.—In all four solvents, viz., nitrobenzene chlorobenzene, tetrachloroethane and toluene were employed. The amount of ester taken was 2 g. in every case and the time employed was two hours. Dry and freshly distilled solvent (7-8 c.c.) was added to finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.4 g.) and the ester added to it. While using nitrobenzene as the solvent, the temperature employed was 80°, but in other three cases it was 100°. Lower temperatures were maintained because of the general observation that the use of solvents lowers the reaction temperature. After the completion of the reaction the usual method was adopted and the ketone was taken up in ether. The solvent used and the ether were removed by distillation at reduced pressure and to the residual oil dilute caustic soda was added. The yellow sodium derivative obtained was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid and the resulting oil taken up in ether, dried and the ether evaporated. The residual oil was dried at 100° and then weighed. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE III

Solvent.	Temperature.	Time.	Yield of the <i>o</i> -hydroxy-ketone.
Nitrobenzene	80°	2 hours	0.43 g.
Chlorobenzene	100°	"	0.51
Tetrachloroethane	100°	"	0.76
Toluene	100°	"	0.61